

Characterisation of the Dielectric Properties of Shea Nut Oil and Oil Impregnated Kraft Paper Insulation for Suitability in Power Transformers

Obande Jonathan Ochigbo

*Department of Electrical Engineering
Bayero University
Kano, Nigeria.*

Nasiru B. Kadandani

*Department of Electrical Engineering
Bayero University
Kano, Nigeria.*

Nuraddeen Magaji

*Department of Electrical Engineering
Bayero University
Kano, Nigeria.*

Sahalu Hassan

*James Watt School of Engineering,
University of Glasgow,
United Kingdom.*

Isiyaku Abubakar

*Department of Electrical Engineering
Bayero University
Kano, Nigeria.*

Sanusi Sani Adamu

*Department of Electrical Engineering
Bayero University
Kano, Nigeria.*

Abstract— Dielectric insulation is critical to the reliability of high-voltage (HV) systems such as transformers and circuit breakers. Mineral oil, the conventional insulating fluid, faces limitations including environmental concerns, flammability and reduced thermal stability. This study evaluates shea nut oil, a biodegradable natural ester, as a sustainable alternative. The oil was purified, kraft paper impregnated and tested following IEC 60156 (AC breakdown voltage, BDV), IEC 60247 (dissipation factor and relative permittivity) and ASTM D445 (viscosity) across 40–100°C. Statistical modelling with Gaussian and Weibull distributions assessed BDV reliability. Shea nut oil outperformed mineral oil, with BDV rising from ~53 kV at 40°C to 63 kV at 100°C—an 8% average advantage—while mineral oil peaked at ~64 kV but showed higher variability. Only shea nut oil passed Weibull fits at all temperatures ($\beta \approx 39$ at 80°C; η 54–66). Its dissipation factor peaked at 0.0025, permittivity declined 3.3–2.9 versus 2.3–2.1 for mineral oil and aging tests showed higher BDV retention (16.5 kV vs. 11.1 kV at 96 h). Despite higher viscosity, shea nut oil demonstrated superior dielectric strength, thermal resilience and aging stability, making it a promising eco-friendly alternative for HV transformers.

Index Terms— Power transformer insulation, Natural ester insulating oil, Breakdown voltage, Weibull distribution, Thermal aging, Insulating liquids, Oil-impregnated kraft paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mineral oil (MO) has been the dominant insulating and cooling medium in power transformers for several decades owing to its satisfactory dielectric strength, thermal performance and economic viability [1], [2]. However, increasing concerns related to environmental sustainability, fire safety and long-term resource availability has stimulated significant research interest in alternative insulating fluids derived from renewable

sources [3], [4], [5]. Among these alternatives, natural ester oils have received considerable attention due to their high biodegradability, elevated flash and fire points and reduced environmental impact compared with conventional mineral oil [6], [7], [2]. Thermal behavior and cooling performance of natural esters also play a critical role in transformer operation and reliability [8].

Despite these advantages, the widespread deployment of natural ester fluids in high-voltage insulation systems remains constrained by uncertainties associated with dielectric reliability, aging behavior and compatibility with solid insulation materials [9], [4], [5]. In oil–paper insulation systems, dielectric performance is governed not only by the intrinsic properties of the insulating liquid but also by its interaction with cellulose-based materials under combined electrical and thermal stresses [10]–[12]. Additional investigations have examined ester–solid insulation compatibility and degradation mechanisms under combined electrical and thermal stresses, underscoring the importance of material interaction in long-term transformer reliability [13], [14], [15].

Consequently, comprehensive experimental characterization, complemented by statistically robust analysis techniques is essential for evaluating the suitability of alternative insulating liquids for transformer applications [16], [17]. Shea nut oil (SNO), a locally available natural ester represents a promising candidate for sustainable transformer insulation due to its renewability and regional availability. Recent studies have indicated that vegetable oil–based esters, including shea-derived oils, can exhibit competitive dielectric and rheological properties when appropriately processed or modified [18], [19]. Additionally, studies have further explored vegetable oil-based

esters and their nanofluid formulations, highlighting improvements in dielectric strength, partial discharge resistance, thermal stability and insulation reliability through material modification and nano-additive incorporation [20], [21]-[26]. However, systematic investigations addressing the dielectric breakdown behaviour, physicochemical characteristics and reliability performance of shea nut oil—particularly under accelerated aging conditions in oil–paper insulation systems—remain limited. Moreover, the inherently stochastic nature of dielectric breakdown in insulating liquids necessitates the application of probabilistic modelling techniques to adequately capture breakdown dispersion and insulation reliability beyond conventional mean-value analysis [27], [28], [29]. Breakdown behavior under impulse and transient voltage stresses has also been reported for conventional and modified insulating oils [30].

In this work, the dielectric performance of shea nut oil is experimentally evaluated and benchmarked against conventional mineral oil in an oil–paper insulation configuration. Standardized experimental procedures, in accordance with IEC and ASTM Standards, are employed to measure AC breakdown voltage, dissipation factor, relative permittivity and kinematic viscosity [31]-[33]. Accelerated thermal aging of oil-impregnated kraft paper is conducted following established thermal endurance guidelines to assess degradation trends representative of transformer operating conditions [34]. To address the random nature of breakdown phenomena, the experimental breakdown voltage data are analysed using a three-parameter Weibull statistical model. This approach enables the determination of characteristic breakdown strength, failure probability and reliability indices at specified percentiles, providing a statistically rigorous basis for insulation assessment [17], [28], [29]. The inclusion of a location parameter allows for estimation of the minimum withstand voltage, thereby offering improved physical interpretation of breakdown behaviour compared with conventional two-parameter Weibull formulations.

The main contributions of this study are threefold: experimental characterization of the dielectric and physicochemical properties of shea nut oil in comparison with mineral oil; evaluation of the aging behaviour of oil-impregnated kraft paper under controlled thermal stress; and application of stochastic Weibull modelling to quantify breakdown reliability and dispersion characteristics. The findings provide insight into the feasibility of shea nut oil as a sustainable insulating fluid for transformer applications and establish a reliability-based methodological framework for the evaluation of alternative dielectric liquids.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

This work investigates the dielectric performance of locally sourced shea nut oil in comparison with conventional mineral oil (Hyrax Oil Sdn. Bhd., Malaysia) for oil–paper insulation systems. All experiments were conducted in compliance with relevant IEC and ASTM standards to ensure repeatability and comparability. The methodology encompasses sample

preparation, dielectric and physicochemical testing and statistical data analysis.

2.1 Sample Preparation and Aging

Oil samples were purified via vacuum degassing, filtration and controlled storage to remove moisture, dissolved gases and contaminants. Kraft paper sheets (0.20 mm thickness, 0.8 g/cm³ density) were vacuum-impregnated with SNO at 5mbar for 3hours to ensure uniform oil absorption and void minimization. After impregnation, samples were stabilized under ambient conditions for 24hrs. Accelerated thermal aging was performed in a vacuum oven ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ accuracy) at 90, 110 and 130°C for a total duration of 96 h. Aging was conducted in sealed conditions to limit oxygen ingress, while pressure and humidity were controlled to simulate transformer operating environments.

2.2 Dielectric and Physicochemical Measurements

This subsection presents a systematic evaluation of the dielectric strength, insulation reliability, and key physicochemical properties of the test oils using standardized measurement protocols. The combined analyses provide a quantitative basis for assessing electrical performance, aging behaviour, and suitability for high-voltage transformer insulation.

2.2.1 AC Breakdown Voltage

The AC breakdown voltage of insulating oils was determined using a BA100 Portable Breakdown Analyzer (B2 electronic GmbH) in accordance with IEC 60156. Oil samples were prepared with ~3% headspace to accommodate air, while mushroom-type spherical electrodes were employed. The test cell and electrodes were meticulously cleaned and rinsed with the same oil to prevent contamination. Electrodes, 12.5–13 mm in diameter were immersed at least 40 mm below the oil surface and kept 12 mm from the cell wall, with a precisely maintained 2.5 ± 0.05 mm gap, thereby minimizing boundary effects and ensuring compliance with IEC requirements.

To eliminate interference from bubbles, the electrode system was oriented horizontally and testing commenced five minutes after filling. A controlled voltage ramp of 2 ± 0.2 kV/s was applied until breakdown occurred. Each sample underwent six breakdown events under identical conditions, with a two-minute pause between tests to stabilize the system. The arithmetic mean of the six breakdown values represented the final BDV, while IEC criteria limited the spread between maximum and minimum values to within 10% of the mean.

2.2.2 Dielectric Dissipation Factor and Relative Permittivity

The dielectric and rheological properties of the insulating oils were evaluated to establish their performance under standardized conditions. Dissipation factor ($\tan \delta$) and relative permittivity were measured using the Agilent PNA-X network analyzer, a high-precision instrument widely employed for dielectric characterization. All measurements adhered to IEC 60247, within the controlled temperature range of 40–100°C. Prior to testing, the oils were purified by vacuum degassing to eliminate dissolved gases and particulates that could distort

dielectric response. The test cell and probe were carefully cleaned, filled to avoid air entrapment and stabilized before data acquisition. During measurement the analyzer introduced a sinusoidal excitation signal, recording reflection (S11) and transmission (S21) coefficients over a frequency sweep. Relative permittivity and $\tan \delta$ were extracted as functions of frequency and temperature, with calibration verified against distilled water as reference material.

Permittivity was determined from (1)

$$\epsilon_r = \epsilon' - j\epsilon'' \quad (1)$$

where:

- ϵ' represents stored energy
- ϵ'' dielectric loss

while the dissipation factor was computed as (2)

$$\tan \delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'. \quad (2)$$

Statistical analysis in Minitab 22 and OriginPro enabled critical evaluation of trends, highlighting both thermal and frequency-dependent behaviours.

2.2.3 Kinematic Viscosity

The kinematic viscosity of the test oils was measured using a Redwood viscometer following ASTM D445 guidelines. The

relationship between viscosity and temperature was modelled using an Arrhenius-type expression as shown in (3)

$$k = Ae^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}} \quad (3)$$

where:

- k = Rate constant of the aging process,
- A = pre-exponential factor (frequency factor),
- E_a = Activation energy (in joules per mole),
- R = Universal gas constant (8.314 J/mol. K)

During testing, the viscometer oil cup was filled to the indicated level and a constant bath temperature was maintained. Once equilibrium was reached, the orifice was opened to allow 50 ml of oil to flow while timing with a stopwatch. The procedure was repeated at least three times for accuracy and the mean flow time was used to calculate kinematic viscosity.

2.3 Summary of Experimental Equipment

Table 1 summarizes the standards, equipment and instruments employed for dielectric characterization, viscosity measurement, oil impregnation and thermal aging. The selected apparatus ensured compliance with IEC and ASTM standards and enabled accurate evaluation of oils under controlled laboratory conditions.

Table 1. Equipment and Standards for Dielectric Characterization of Oil

S/No.	Parameter/Test	Standards	Equipment/Instrument	Purpose/Description
1	AC Breakdown Voltage (BDV) Test	IEC 60156	Breakdown Voltage Tester (BAUR BA100), Samgor YDQW100kV/5kVA Transformer	Measures dielectric strength of insulating liquids under AC stress
2	Dissipation Factor (Tan Delta) and Permittivity	IEC 60247	Dielectric Analyzer / Agilent PNA-X Network Analyzer	Determines energy losses and polarization properties in the fluid
3	Viscosity Measurement	ASTM D445	Subi Tek Redwood Viscometer	Determines fluid flow resistance, linked to thermal performance
4	Thermal Aging of Kraft Paper	IEC 60216 / IEC 60156	Berkeley Scientific Vacuum Oven VT 6025 (with temperature control)	Simulates long-term thermal stress on impregnated paper
5	Oil Impregnation Process	–	Vacuum Chamber & Impregnation Setup	Facilitates complete saturation of kraft paper with shea nut oil

2. 4.1

2. 4 Theoretical and Statistical Background

This subsection outlines the physical principles and stochastic frameworks governing dielectric breakdown in insulating liquids. Deterministic electric-field relations are complemented by three-parameter Weibull statistical modeling to account for variability, threshold effects, and reliability behavior, providing a rigorous basis for interpreting breakdown voltage measurements and percentile-based insulation performance.

Dielectric Breakdown in Insulating Liquids

The mathematical modelling of the breakdown voltage of a dielectric liquid involves understanding the relationship between the breakdown voltage and various factors that influence the dielectric behaviour of the liquid under an applied electric field. This includes physical, chemical and electrical properties of the liquid as well as external conditions such as electrode geometry, temperature, pressure and contamination. The choice of model depends on the specific properties of the liquid, the application context and the available experimental data. For gases, Paschen's Law describes the breakdown voltage as a function of pressure and gap distance, as shown in (4). While primarily derived for gases, similar principles can

be adapted for liquids.

$$V_b = \frac{B.p.d}{\ln(A.p.d) - \ln\left(\ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{\gamma}\right)\right)} \quad (4)$$

where:

- V_b : Breakdown voltage
- d : Distance between electrodes
- p : Pressure
- A, B : Constants specific to the liquid
- γ : Secondary ionization coefficient

For a dielectric material, the breakdown voltage can also be influenced by the dielectric strength (E_{ds}), which is the maximum electric field the material can withstand without breakdown. Therefore, the breakdown voltage can be modelled as shown in (5).

$$V_b = E_{ds} \cdot d \quad (5)$$

where:

- V_b = breakdown voltage (V)
- E_{ds} = dielectric strength of the material (V/m)
- d = distance between electrodes (m)

This model indicates that the breakdown voltage is directly proportional to both the dielectric strength of the liquid and the distance between the electrodes.

2.4.2 Stochastic Modelling of BDV Using the Three-Parameter Weibull Distribution

Due to the inherently random and probabilistic nature of dielectric breakdown events in insulating fluids, this study adopts a stochastic statistical modelling approach. Specifically, the three-parameter Weibull distribution was used to model the BDV data for shea nut oil and mineral oil. The stochastic approach allows for a more realistic evaluation of insulation reliability by capturing the uncertainty and variability associated with experimental measurements. The model assumes that BDV events follow a Weibull-type statistical distribution and enables the estimation of characteristic breakdown voltages, reliability levels and failure rates at specified percentiles [28].

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the three-parameter Weibull model employed in this work is defined in (6)

$$F(V) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{V-\gamma}{\alpha}\right)^\beta\right] \quad (6)$$

where:

- $F(V)$: Cumulative probability that breakdown occurs at or below voltage
- V : Breakdown voltage of the insulating oil sample.
- γ : Location parameter — minimum voltage below which no breakdown occurs.
- η : Scale parameter — spreads the distribution; akin to a “characteristic breakdown voltage.”
- β : Shape parameter — governs failure rate behaviour ($\beta > 1$ indicates wear-out, etc.).

Log-Likelihood Function:

Given a sample of breakdown voltage observations V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n with:

- F : set of failed samples (with observed breakdown)
- C : set of censored samples (no breakdown occurred up to a limit)

The log-likelihood function for a *three-parameter Weibull distribution* (shape = β , scale = η , location = γ) with failure data F and censored data C is given as (7)

$$\ln L(\theta|V) = \sum_{i \in F} [\ln(\beta) + (\beta - 1) \ln(V_i - \gamma) - \beta \ln \eta - \left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta] + \sum_{i \in C} \left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta \quad (7)$$

To obtain optimal estimates of the Weibull parameters β, η and γ , the partial derivatives of the log-likelihood function with respect to each parameter were evaluated and equated to zero, as shown in (8)-(10), respectively. These nonlinear equations were solved numerically to determine the Weibull parameters reported in the Results section.

Derivative with respect to β :

$$\frac{\partial \ln L(\theta|t)}{\partial \beta} = \sum_{i \in F} \left[\frac{1}{\beta} + \ln(V_i - \gamma) - \ln \eta - \left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta \ln\left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right) \right] + \sum_{i \in C} \left[-\left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta \ln\left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right) \right] = 0 \quad (8)$$

Derivative with respect to η :

$$\frac{\partial \ln L(\theta|t)}{\partial \eta} = \sum_{i \in F} \left[-\frac{\beta}{\eta} + \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta \right] + \sum_{i \in C} \left[\frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta \right] = 0 \quad (9)$$

Derivative with respect to γ :

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \gamma} = \sum_{i \in F} \left[-\frac{\beta-1}{V_i - \gamma} + \beta \left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^{\beta-1} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta} \right] + \sum_{i \in C} \left[\beta \left(\frac{V_i - \gamma}{\eta}\right)^{\beta-1} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta} \right] = 0 \quad (10)$$

The adoption of the three-parameter Weibull distribution, rather than the conventional two-parameter model, is justified by the presence of a non-zero breakdown threshold in insulating liquids, particularly under controlled laboratory conditions. The inclusion of the location parameter (γ) allows the model to capture the minimum withstand voltage below which breakdown does not occur, thereby improving goodness-of-fit and providing a more physically meaningful representation of BDV behaviour. This is reflected in the Weibull probability

plots and reliability curves presented in the Results section, where the three-parameter model yields reduced data scatter and more accurate percentile-based reliability estimates compared to the two-parameter formulation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dielectric behaviour of SNO and its performance in oil-impregnated kraft paper relative to conventional MO was examined with the aim of establishing its suitability for power transformer insulation. Emphasis was placed on breakdown voltage, dissipation factor, relative permittivity, viscosity and aging behaviour across a wide temperature range. Statistical reliability analysis using Gaussian and Weibull distributions were employed.

3.1. Breakdown Voltage Distributions

The evolution of AC breakdown voltage with temperature provides a key metric of insulating oil robustness. **Figs 1(a)–**

(m) show BDV distributions for SNO and MO across 40–100°C. At 40°C, MO exhibits wider scatter and lower modal values, indicating greater susceptibility to premature breakdown, whereas SNO’s polar molecular structure yields tighter, more reproducible distributions [2]. Between 50–70°C, BDV increases for both oils due to reduced viscosity and enhanced dissipation of gas bubbles, yet SNO maintains narrow, symmetric histograms while MO develops extended low-voltage tails, reflecting localized weaknesses [22]. At 80–100°C, differences become pronounced: SNO sustains high average BDV with compact distributions, while MO shows broad, irregular histograms as thermal stress accelerates dielectric degradation [14]. Overall, SNO demonstrates superior breakdown strength and statistical reliability, supporting its role as a thermally resilient, sustainable transformer insulating fluid.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

(l)

(m)

(n)

Fig. 1. (a)– (m) Histograms of AC BDV for SNO and MO over the 40–100°C range.

3.2. Weibull Distribution Analysis

Weibull distribution analysis was employed to assess the statistical reliability of BDV data for SNO and MO. This approach provides clarity into failure probability, scale and shape parameters thereby enabling a robust comparison of insulation performance consistency across varying operating temperatures.

3.2.1 Weibull probability distribution for Shea Nut Oil

The AC breakdown voltage of SNO over 40–100 °C was analyzed using a three-parameter Weibull distribution [28], capturing the inherent randomness of dielectric breakdown events as shown in **Fig. 2**. The characteristic breakdown voltage η rises with temperature—from 54.06 kV at 40°C to 65.85 kV at 100°C—reflecting improved dielectric strength due to lower viscosity and more effective dissipation of bubbles and moisture. The shape parameter β increases at higher temperatures, indicating reduced scatter and more predictable breakdown behaviour. Goodness-of-fit tests ($p > 0.05$) confirm the Weibull model adequately represents the data. Probabilistic analyses provide conservative, practically relevant estimates for low-percentile failure probabilities, which are critical for transformer insulation design and reliability assessment [12], [13]. Overall, SNO demonstrates high statistical reliability, supporting its potential as a sustainable alternative to conventional mineral oils in high-voltage applications.

3.2.2 Weibull probability distribution for Mineral Oil

The Weibull distribution of AC breakdown voltage for MO over 40–100°C is illustrated in **Fig. 3**. At lower temperatures (40–60°C), the scale parameter η remains modest (52.37–56.72 kV), reflecting the influence of residual moisture and entrapped gases that promote early breakdown. The shape parameter β shows broad scatter (17.19 at 40°C; 8.84 at 50°C), consistent with higher viscosity and greater impurity impact [24]. With rising temperature, η increases steadily, reaching 64.82 kV at 100 °C, while β improves markedly ($\beta = 39.38$), producing steeper slopes and narrower distributions indicative of more predictable dielectric performance. Goodness-of-fit tests (AD, $p > 0.05$) confirm Weibull modeling accurately represents low-percentile failure risks. Comparative plots with SNO show consistently higher η and β for SNO, reflecting narrower distributions, lower variability and superior reliability under thermal stress.

This enhanced performance is attributed to the polar molecular structure of natural esters, improving intermolecular cohesion and compatibility with cellulose insulation, consistent with trends observed in ester-based nanofluids and bio-based liquid composites [13], [25], [28].

Fig. 2. Weibull Distribution of AC BDV Percentiles for Shea Nut Oil

Fig. 3. Weibull Distribution of AC BDV Percentiles for Mineral Oil

3.3 Breakdown Strength

Fig. 4 presents the AC breakdown strength of SNO and MO impregnated kraft paper over thermal aging intervals of 24–96 hours.

Fig. 4. Comparison of Breakdown Strength in Shea nut and Mineral oils

At 24 hrs, SNO exhibits superior dielectric performance (~23 kV/mm) versus MO (~20 kV/mm), reflecting enhanced initial impregnation and reinforcement due to its higher polarity and ester content, which improves cellulose compatibility and pore filling [29].

Both oils show gradual strength decline with aging; after 96 hrs, SNO retains ~16 kV/mm, whereas MO falls below 12 kV/mm, consistent with its lower oxidative stability and formation of acidic byproducts that accelerate degradation [12]. SNO also demonstrates narrower standard deviation margins throughout, indicating reduced variability and more predictable performance. MO exhibits broader scatter, particularly beyond 72 hrs, highlighting localized weak points and unstable aging pathways. These trends align with Weibull analyses, where natural esters typically yield higher shape factors (β), signifying enhanced reliability and lower failure probability [13], [29].

3.4. Temperature Dependence of Dielectric Dissipation Factor ($\tan \delta$)

Fig. 5 shows the dissipation factor of SNO and MO across the investigated temperature range. SNO consistently exhibits lower $\tan \delta$ than MO, indicating reduced dielectric losses and improved insulation stability. At 40 °C, both oils display low loss factors; however, MO rises sharply with temperature, reflecting enhanced conduction due to polar oxidation by-products—an increase in dissipation factor being a well-established indicator of oil degradation. In contrast, SNO increases gradually, demonstrating superior thermal oxidation resistance and sustained dielectric performance.

These trends suggest that SNO not only reduces energy dissipation but also enhances insulation reliability, supporting longer transformer service life. The behaviour aligns with prior studies on natural esters and ester-based dielectric fluids, which report lower dielectric losses and improved stability compared to petroleum-based oils [18], [8], [5].

Fig. 5. Graph of Dissipation Factor ($\tan \delta$) of Shea nut and Mineral oils

3.5 Temperature Influence on Relative Permittivity

Fig. 6. shows the relative permittivity of SNO and MO over 40–100°C, a key parameter governing insulation performance and electric field distribution

Fig. 6. Graph of Relative Permittivity of Shea nut and Mineral oils

SNO maintains a high and stable permittivity, starting at ≈ 3.2 at 40°C and decreasing slightly to ≈ 3.0 at 100°C, reflecting strong thermal resilience and consistent dielectric behaviour. In contrast, MO declines from ≈ 2.4 to ≈ 2.0 across the same range, indicative of thermal degradation and diminished insulation capability. The superior stability of SNO's permittivity under thermal stress underscores its suitability as a transformer insulating medium, enhancing capacitive performance and electric field uniformity. These observations align with prior studies highlighting the dielectric robustness of natural esters compared to mineral oils [15], [8], [5].

3.6 Temperature Dependence of Viscosity

The viscosity of SNO and MO as a function of temperature is shown in Figure 7, illustrating distinct thermal behaviors relevant to transformer insulation performance. Viscosity is a key parameter governing fluid circulation, heat transfer and operational reliability in high-voltage systems. SNO exhibits a relatively high viscosity of approximately 40 mm²/s at 40 °C,

which decreases sharply to about 15 mm²/s at 100°C. This pronounced temperature dependence is characteristic of natural esters and reflects their molecular structure, promoting improved fluid mobility and enhanced heat dissipation at elevated temperatures [6], [8].

Fig. 7. Graph of Viscosity of Shea nut and Mineral oils

In contrast, MO shows a much lower initial viscosity (≈ 10 mm²/s at 40°C) and only a slight reduction to around 5 mm²/s at 100°C. Although favorable for flow at lower temperatures, this limited thermal sensitivity may constrain effective heat removal under high-load operating conditions. Overall, the strong temperature-dependent viscosity reduction of SNO indicates superior thermal adaptability, contributing to improved lubrication, dielectric reliability and cooling performance in transformer applications.

4. CONCLUSION

This study provides preliminary evidence that SNO has strong potential as a locally sourced natural ester for transformer insulation. The results demonstrate encouraging dielectric performance and reliability indicators, suggesting that SNO can meet key functional requirements for high-voltage applications. The significance of this work lies in its focus on SNO, an underexplored ester, thereby addressing an important knowledge gap in sustainable insulating fluids research. While the findings are promising, comprehensive validation is still required before large-scale deployment. Future investigations should emphasize long-term aging behaviour, compatibility with transformer materials, impulse breakdown characteristics and formulation enhancement, including nanoparticle modification. Overall, this research establishes a foundational framework for continued development and positions Shea Nut Oil as a viable candidate for environmentally sustainable and reliable transformer insulation systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Dielectric Insulation Laboratory, School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering (SEE) Univerisiti Sains Malaysia (USM) for providing essential equipment and technical support. Their support provided the essential resources and opportunity to accomplish this research successfully.

FUNDING INFORMATION

Funding for this work was provided by the Federal Government of Nigeria through the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Y. Ushakov, A. V. Mytnikov and I. U. Rakhmonov, *High-Voltage Equipment of Power Systems. Power Systems*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2023. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-38252-9.
- [2] I. Fofana, "50 years in the development of insulating liquids," *IEEE Electr. Insul. Mag.*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 13–25, 2013.
- [3] M. Rafiq *et al.*, "Sustainable, renewable and environmental-friendly insulation systems for high voltages applications," *Molecules*, vol. 25, no. 17, p. 3901, 2020.
- [4] B. A. Tlhabologo, R. Samikannu and M. Mosalaosi, "Alternative liquid dielectrics in power transformer insulation: A review," *Indones. J. Electr. Eng. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1761–1777, 2021.
- [5] M. Rafiq, M. Shafique, M. Ateeq, M. Zink and D. Targitay, "Natural esters as sustainable alternating dielectric liquids for transformer insulation system: Analyzing the state of the art," *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 623–659, 2024.
- [6] M. Lashbrook, A. Gyore and R. Martin, "A review of the fundamental dielectric characteristics of ester-based dielectric liquids," *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 202, pp. 121–129, 2017.
- [7] H. Wang *et al.*, "Research on fire safety and environmental characteristics of green synthetic ester," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Electr. Energy Convers. Syst. Control (IEECSC)*, May 2025, pp. 986–990.
- [8] G. Dombek, Z. Nadolny and A. Marcinkowska, "Thermal properties of natural ester and low viscosity natural ester in the aspect of the reliable operation of the transformer cooling system," *Eksplot. Niezawodn.*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 384–391, 2019.
- [9] A. Montero, B. García, J. C. Burgos and C. González-García, "Dielectric design of ester-filled power transformers: AC stress analysis," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 2403–2412, Jun. 2022.
- [10] J. Sanz, C. J. Renedo, A. Ortiz, P. J. Quintanilla, F. Ortiz and D. F. García, "A brief review of the impregnation process with dielectric fluids of cellulosic materials used in electric power transformers," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 9, p. 3673, 2023.
- [11] G. T. Naidu, U. M. Rao and S. Suresh, "Influence of ester liquids on dielectric strength of cellulose kraft paper," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 3, p. 762, 2022.
- [12] C. Fernández-Diego *et al.*, "Damage assessment of transformer Kraft paper insulation aged in mineral and vegetable oils," *Cellulose*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 2653–2672, 2019.
- [13] Y. Qian, Q. Wang, Y. Zhao, L. Peng and Y. Pan, "Study on the compatibility of natural esters with solid materials for transformers," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Electr. Energy Convers. Syst. Control (IEECSC)*, May 2025, pp. 876–880.
- [14] B. Qi *et al.*, "Dielectric and microstructural deterioration process of resin-impregnated paper materials under electrical-thermal combined stress," *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TDEI.2025.3559452.
- [15] C. Williamson *et al.*, "Investigation of impulsive breakdown of interfaces formed by ester insulating liquids and solid dielectrics," unpublished.
- [16] M. Rafiq and M. Shafique, "HVDC transformer insulation system: Present research, trends, challenges and prospects," *e-Prime – Adv. Electr. Eng., Electron. Energy*, p. 100874, 2024.
- [17] D. Kanumuri, A. Kumar, N. Baruah and S. K. Nayak, "Influence of thermal aging on DC conductivity and breakdown strength of natural ester oils for HVDC applications," *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 3444–3452, Dec. 2024.
- [18] A. K. Das, "Analysis of AC breakdown strength of vegetable oils and effect of mineral oil," *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 214, p. 108920, 2023.
- [19] A. Aliyu, S. Umar, A. A. Abdelmalik, H. Abdulsalam, S. S. Maidawa and S. A. Suleiman, "Effect of silica and alumina nanoparticles addition on the dielectric and rheological properties of shea oil methyl ester," *UMYU Scientifica*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 70–75, 2024.

- [20] A. Siddique *et al.*, “Sustainable insulating materials for high-voltage equipment: Dielectric properties of green synthesis-based nanofluids from vegetable oils,” *Sustainability*, vol. 17, no. 4, p. 1740, 2025.
- [21] S. O. Oparanti, E. O. Obebe, I. Fofana and R. Jafari, “A state-of-the-art review on the potential of waste cooking oil as a sustainable insulating liquid for green transformers,” *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 15, no. 14, p. 7631, 2025.
- [22] R. A. Farade, N. I. A. Wahab and D. E. A. Mansour, “The effect of nano-additives in natural ester dielectric liquids: A comprehensive review on dielectric properties,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 1502–1516, Aug. 2023.
- [23] K. N. Koutras *et al.*, “Breakdown performance and partial discharge development in transformer oil-based metal carbide nanofluids,” *Nanomaterials*, vol. 12, no. 2, p. 269, 2022.
- [24] T. Sudhakar, R. Muniraj, T. Jarin and S. Sumathi, “Nanofluid-enhanced vegetable oil blends: A sustainable approach to breakthroughs in dielectric liquid insulation for electrical systems,” *Biomass Convers. Biorefin.*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 9011–9034, 2025.
- [25] R. A. Farade, N. I. Abdul Wahab, V. U. Siddiqui and S. M. Sapuan, “Bio-based liquid nanocomposites for electrical equipment,” *Phys. Sci. Rev.*, <https://doi.org/10.1515/psr-2024-0077>
- [26] S. M. W. Masra *et al.*, “A systematic review on promising development of palm oil and its nanofluid as a biodegradable oil insulation alternative,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 302–318, Feb. 2022.
- [27] R. Zhang *et al.*, “Bubbles in transformer oil: Dynamic behavior, internal discharge and triggered liquid breakdown,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 86–94, Feb. 2022.
- [28] N. S. Suhaimi *et al.*, “Performance evaluation of natural ester oils as sustainable dielectric fluids for transformers: AI enhanced statistical analysis,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, 2024, doi: 10.1109/TDEI.2024.3516701
- [29] A. Cianna, S. Sumathi and T. Jarin, “Analysis of properties and statistical study on partial discharge inception voltage using normal and Weibull distributions for vegetable oil-based nanofluids,” *Biomass Convers. Biorefin.*, vol. 14, no. 14, pp. 16725–16742, 2024.
- [30] B. Vijayarani *et al.*, “Breakdown voltage performance of transformer oil under impulse voltage: An experimental approach,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Inventive Mater. Sci. Appl. (ICIMA)*, May 2025, pp. 150–157.
- [31] International Electrotechnical Commission, *IEC 60156: Insulating Liquids – Determination of the Breakdown Voltage at Power Frequency – Test Method*, Geneva, Switzerland: IEC, 2018.
- [32] International Electrotechnical Commission, *IEC 60247: Insulating Liquids – Measurement of Relative Permittivity, Dielectric Dissipation Factor ($\tan \delta$) and DC Resistivity*, Geneva, Switzerland: IEC, 2017.
- [33] ASTM International, *ASTM D445-21: Standard Test Method for Kinematic Viscosity of Transparent and Opaque Liquids (and Calculation of Dynamic Viscosity)*, West Conshohocken, PA, USA: ASTM, 2021.
- [34] International Electrotechnical Commission, *IEC 60216: Electrical Insulating Materials – Thermal Endurance Properties*, Geneva, Switzerland: IEC, 2013.